

Nominalization in Japanese and Uyghur: A Comparative Study of *koto* and *-maq/-sh/-ghan/-lik*

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Abstract

This work offers an account for the different nominalization strategies between Japanese and Uyghur, that in the two languages nominalization can be made possible via suffix-like elements. One of the most intriguing facts regarding their differences lies in the inventory of nominalization suffixes, as Japanese allows a variety of nominalizations using the universal nominalizer *koto*, Uyghur seeks 4 distinct suffixes to do so. In the wake of a scrutiny of the linguistic data of the two languages, we follow the idea of Hara et al. (2013) that Japanese *koto* can merge to different syntactic positions, which ultimately yields different nominalization-related interpretations. As to the 4 nominal suffixes in Uyghur, we conclude that they all demonstrate different syntactic behaviors and characteristics, alongside with nonidentical distributions, thus it is expected they would generate very different nominalizations.

1. Introduction

Nominalization is widely attested crosslinguistically, allowing verbal predicate to function as nominal expressions. There are a number of different strategies in terms of how nominalizations exactly happen. Both Japanese and Uyghur entail productive nominalization strategies, whereas showing significant difference in structural and semantic natures. In Japanese, the nominalizer *koto* has been analyzed as clausal or AspP-level, capable of denoting eventive or propositional interpretations (Hara et al. 2013). However, Uyghur lacks such universal nominalizer and employs three different nominalizers, namely, *-maq/-sh/-ghan/-lik* to cover the range of *koto*.

This squib investigates how these nominalizers compare across two languages. In particular, the very properties of them will be closely examined with respect to their formal and semantic behaviors. We argue that Japanese *koto* operates on both NP and CP level, which yields semantic ambiguity as Hara et al. (2013) suggest; while Uyghur nominalizers are distributed across various syntactic positions. Specifically, *-maq* and *-sh* are primarily event/action-denoting, whereas forms such as *-ghan* and *-lik* encode propositional content. As a result, Uyghur nominalizers exhibit distinct semantic interpretations respectively, unlike *koto*. In addition, we propose that although *-ghan* bears innate temporal reference,

it interacts with higher functional head to determine whether it reflects past tense or perfectivity. These differences stated above present a broader typological contrast in how nominalization is realized across languages.

The paper is organized as follows; in Section 2, we will present a thorough review of linguistic facts concerning the two languages, particularly the less-studied Uyghur. Section 3 comprises of our main proposals, in which all 4 Uyghur nominalizers receive an account regarding their syntactic properties and distributions. Section 4 concludes this squib.

2. Linguistic data

2.1 *Koto* in Japanese

First, let us take a quick rundown of *koto* in Japanese. Etymologically, *koto* derives from the noun *koto* “thing”, which is still used as a noun proper. Researches on nominalizing *koto* date back to Kuroda (1965) and it is generally accepted that it denotes propositional content, as illustrated in (1):

- (1). 彼が来たことを知っている
kare-ga ki-ta koto-o shitte-iru.
he-NOM come-PAST NOML-ACC know.be-PRES
'I know that he came.'

Notice that what has been nominalized is a complete clause which comprises of subject and finite verb. Furthermore, as the accusative case-marking *-o* shows, the entire clause becomes the object of *shiru* “to know”, a bridge verb. At this point, it is fairly safe to say that *koto* is positioned at CP-level (propositional content included), as assumed in the literature¹.

Following the propositional *koto*-nominalizer shown above, it is observed by Hara et al. (2013) that *koto*-nominalization can also be eventive. See the following example:

- (2). 私はパンを食べることが好きだ
watashi-wa pan-o tabe-ru koto-ga suki da.
I-TOP bread-ACC eat-PRES NOML-NOM like be
'I like eating bread.'

¹ Hara et al. (2013) propose that propositional *koto*-nominal is a TP that represents a proposition/fact. Our proposal, however, should not be considered an opponent to their analysis as either TP-approach or CP-approach stems from the propositional interpretation invoked by *koto*. We follow the CP-approach because sometimes TP is not inclusive enough to cover a proposition as in (i):

- (i) John wants [me to go].

The infinite TP in (i) is not an independent proposition by itself. Thus, we take the liberty to call *koto*-nominalizer in such cases as CP-level.

In (2), the nominalized clause is taken to be the object of the verb *suki*, and the nominalized content is clearly an event “I eat bread” instead of a proposition that has truth-value.

Additionally, there is another kind of *koto*-nominalization we believe is more closely related to the eventive-*koto* rather than the propositional one. As illustrated in (3), what has been nominalized is a generic/abstract action which often involves judgement. This pattern of nominalization is quite similar to Uyghur *-sh*, to which we will return in Section 3.

- (3). パンを食べることはいい
 Pan-o tabe-ru koto-ga ii.
 Bread-ACC eat-PRES NOML-NOM good
 ‘Eating bread is good.’

2.2 Nominalizers in Uyghur

As mentioned above, Uyghur employs three distinct nominalizing constructions to differentiate propositional and eventive contents. In Section 2.2, we will present a general picture of their basic syntactic/semantic properties. In (4-6), the three nominalizing constructions are explicitly demonstrated, entailing *-ghan*, *-sh*, *-maq* and *-lik*. As each translations shows, these examples should be seen as the semantic counterparts of *koto*-nominalizations presented in 2.1.

- (4). ئۇنىڭ كەلگىنىنى بىلىمەن (-ghan)
 u-ning kel-gen-i-ni bil-i-men
 (s)he-GEN come-NOML-POSS.3rd-ACC know-PRES-1st
 ‘I know that he came.’
- (5). مەن نان يېيىشنى ياخشى كۆرىمەن (-sh)
 men nan ye-yish-ni yaxshi kör-i-men
 I bread eat-NOML-ACC good see-PRES-1st
 ‘I like eating bread.’
- (6). نان يېمەك ياخشى (-maq)
 nan ye-mek yaxshi
 Bread eat-NOML good
 ‘Eating bread is good.’

2.2.1 the case of *-ghan*

It is desirable for readers to keep in mind that we call *-ghan* (as well as its allomorph *-ken*, *-gen*, and *-qan*) a nominalizer only for expository purpose, because it originates from the past/perfect tense suffix². Aside from the usage like (4), we can also find *-ghan* in cases like

² The tense/aspect interpretation regarding *-ghan* is an ongoing debate. See Asarina 2011, Major 2014 and Li 2025 for related discussion. We will not elaborate on this matter because it is irrelevant of the present discussion.

(7):

- (7). مەن بازارغا بارغان
Men bazar-gha bar-ghan
I market-DAT go-PERF
'I went/have gone to the market.'

Hence, it would not be surprising that the English translation of (4) involves a past tense verb *came*. *-ghan* may also be used as a part of relative clause. As (8) shows, the complementizer-less relative clause only contains two words: *my* and *have drunken*.

- (8). مەنسك ئىچكەن [چايم ياخشى]
[me-ning ich-ken] chay-m jaxshi
I-GEN drink-PERF tea-POSS.1st good
'The tea that I have drunken is good.'

On the basis of the data given above, we may reach the generalization that *ghan*-suffixed verb can indeed serve as a nominal, especially in the nominalization construction in (4). Uyghur genitive nouns must cooccur with a person-specified possessive noun to yield correct possessive structure, and this requirement is signaled by the fact that the subject is followed by the genitive suffix *-neng* while *kel-gen* is suffixed by the third person possessive *-i*. On top of that, *kel-gen* is ended with *-ni*, the accusative case-marking suffix, which further indicates that this predicate is now the object of the verb *bilimen*.

These uses suggest that *-ghan* spans multiple functional domains, including relative modification, nominalization, and predication. While it originates as a participial form, it exhibits properties associated with both nominal and clausal structures. This distribution raises the question of how the temporal and clausal properties of *-ghan* are derived, an issue that will be addressed in later sections.

2.2.2 the case of *-sh*

The suffix *-sh* is a productive nominalizer in Uyghur that derives event-denoting nouns from verbal predicates³. Unlike *-ghan*, which exhibits both nominal and aspectual/temporal properties, *-sh* primarily yields nominal expressions with limited clausal structure.

As (5) suggests, repeated here as (9), the predicate *ye* "to eat" functions as the object of *jaxshi kör* "to like", because it is ended with the accusative case-marking suffix *-ni*.

- (9). مەن نان يېيىشنى ياخشى كۆرىمەن
men nan ye-yish-ni jaxshi kör-i-men.

³ It should be noted that a formally similar suffix also appears in certain verbal derivations (e.g., cooperative or reciprocal readings). While the relationship between these uses and nominalization is not fully understood, their coexistence may suggest that *-ish* is associated with a lower verbal domain. Since the present work is on nominalization, we will not leave the related discussion open.

I bread eat-NOML-ACC good see-PRES-1st
 'I like eating bread.'

It is also worth noticing that *ish*-suffixed predicate can appear as the possessive-nominal of a genitive noun. And this use should not be surprising, since any ordinary nominal should be able to do so:

(10). مېنىڭ كىتاب ئوقۇشۇم
 Men-ing kitab oqu-sh-um.
 I-GEN book read-NOML-POSS.1st
 'My reading book.'

The similarity between *-ghan* and *-sh* is then rather clear: both of them have capacity to preserve the argument structure of the base verb while encoding these arguments through possessive morphology rather than nominative-accusative case marking. But their differences also stand out; for one thing, *-sh* nominalizations do not encode tense, which sharply contrast *-ghan* in sentences like (8). And a nominalized predicate like (11) is utterly ill-formed:

(11). باردىش*
 *bar-di-sh
 go-Past.3rd-NOML
 Intended reading: 'That (s)he went.'

Illustrated in (11), the suffix *-sh* cannot attach to tensed verbal forms, suggesting that it operates on a lower, non-finite verbal domain. This restriction indicates that *-sh* nominalization applies below the level of tense, targeting a non-finite verbal projection (probably v*P)⁴.

Following the non-temporal property of *-sh*, it also differs from *-ghan*—a propositional nominalizer— in that it conveys an eventive reading. This point can be verified on two pieces of empirical evidence: (i) truth-valueness; as the translations in (4-6) and (8-10) suggest, what is *ish*-nominalized can neither be verified or falsified, proving its truth-value neutrality, which is not the case regarding *ghan*-nominalization. (ii) compatibility with factive verbs (Kiparsky & Kiparsky 1970) like *bil* "to know".

(12). مەن ئۇنىڭ كېلىشىنى بىلىمەن?
 ?Men u-ning kel-sh-i-ni bil-i-men.

⁴ It is possible for *ish*-suffixed nominals to appear in a tensed context, where the matrix predicate, instead of *ish*-suffixed predicate, takes on the temporal morphemes. As suggested by (ii), nominalized predicate can be subjugated to a past tense predicate.

(ii) ئۇ يۈگۈرۈشى باشلىدى
 U yügür-üş-ni bashlidi.
 (s)he run-NOML-ACC started-PAST.3rd
 '(s)he started to run'

I (s)he-GEN come-NOML-POSS.3rd-ACC know-PRES.1st
 Intended reading: 'I know about his coming.'

In (12), the *ish*-nominalized predicated is associated with the factive verb *bil*, resulting in clear drop of well-formedness comparing to its *-ghan* counterpart in (4). If *ish*-nominalization is not fully compatible with factive verb, which often entails a proposition rather than an event, one would expect *ish*-nominalization to occur unproblematically with desiderative verbs like *ümid qil* "to wish", as (13) exhibits, which is the case:

(13). مەن ئۇنىڭ كېلىشىنى ئۈمىد قىلىمەن
 Men u-ning kel-sh-i-ni ümid qil-i-men.
 I (s)he-GEN come-NOML-POSS.3rd hope do-PRES.1st
 'I wish his coming.'

In this subsection, we have witnessed that *-sh* functions as an event nominalizer, suggesting it is tense/aspect neutral, while *-ghan* is associated with propositional interpretation, equipped with innate temporal-aspectual anchoring that explains its compatibility with factive predicate.

2.2.3 the case of *-maq*

There is another nominalizer *-maq* that can be observed in examples like (6), repeated as (14). At first glance, *-maq* and *-sh* share a number of similarities in terms of nominalization strategy. For one thing, the sentence in (15) indicates that *maq*-suffixed predicate can hardly yield desirable results when cooccur with a factive matrix predicate (recall *-sh* also gives rise to marginality). In other words, both of them lack propositional force, distinguishing them from *-ghan* nominalizations.

(14). نان يېمەك ياخشى
 Nan ye-mek yaxshi.
 Bread eat-NOML good
 'Eating bread is good.'

(15). *مەن ئۇنىڭ كەلماق بىلىمەن*
 *Men u-ning kel-maq bil-i-men.
 I (s)he-GEN come-NOML know-PRES.1st
 'I know about his coming.'

Another similarity between *-maq* and *-sh* is that they do not encode tense anchoring. Thus, a nominalized predicate constructed in (16) should be ruled out, just like its *ish*-counterpart in (11):

(16). *باردىماق*
 *bar-di-maq
 go-Past.3rd-NOML

Intended reading: ‘That (s)he went.’

However, despite the shared properties, *-maq* and *-sh* differ in their semantic interpretation and distribution. First, *maq*-suffixed predicate only partially meets the diagnoses of Davidsonian event (see Davidson 1967 among many others). To exemplify this fact, observe the following sentences in which *maq*-suffixed predicates are modified by various adverbs:

(17). تۈنۈگۈن بازارغا بېرىش
Tünügen bazar-gha ber-*sh*.
yesterday market-DAT go-NOML
‘That I went to the market yesterday.’

(18). تۈنۈگۈن بازارغا بارماق?
?Tünügen bazar-gha bar-*maq*.
yesterday market-DAT go-NOML
‘That I went to the market yesterday.’

(19). تېز يۈگۈرۈش ياخشى
Tez yügür-üş jaxshi
fast run-NOML good
‘Running fast is good’

(20). تېز يۈگۈرمەك ياخشى تېز?
Tez yügür-mek jaxshi
fast run-NOML good
‘Running fast is good’

It should be clarified that (18) and (20) should not be taken to be ungrammatical, but it is obvious that the adverbs involved are not modifying an *event*. In the case of (17-18), *maq*-suffixed (17) is canonically associated with context like “As of yesterday, it might (not) be a good idea to go to the market”, to put it differently, *-maq* actually encodes generic reading (event type); on the other hand, since *ish*-suffixed (18) describes a specific event (event token), what is referred to must be the event time of “going”. Likewise, while (19) implicitly suggests “this time/under such circumstances”, (20) addresses generic evaluation.

The event vs. generic reading contrast can be more easily observed with the verb *bashla* “to start”. As shown by (21-22), unlike event-denoting *-sh*, *-maq* is barred from such contexts. This should not be a novel finding, since *-maq* fails to express eventive interpretation invoked by *start*-like verbs. These differences suggest that *-sh* projects an eventive structure (e.g., vP), while *-maq* occupies a lower, more lexical domain, which we will return to in Section 3.

(21). ئۇ يۈگۈرۈشنى باشلىدى
U yügür-üş-ni bashl-idi.
(s)he run-NOML-ACC started-PAST.3rd

‘(s)he started to run.’

(22). ئۇ يۈگۈرمەك باشلىدى *

*U yügür-mek bashl-idi.

(s)he run-NOML-ACC started-PAST.3rd

‘(s)he started to run.’

In sum, *-sh* and *-maq* differ in that the former encodes eventive nominalization, while the latter expresses actions as abstract concepts. This distinction is reflected in their interaction with predicates, temporal modification, and modality.

2.2.4 the case of *-lik*

The last nominalizer we will address is *-lik*, which is a very productive suffix that can yield derivative adjective, noun and adverbs (see Niita 2015) as illustrated below in (23-25). Therefore, it might seem misleading to call *-lik* nominalizer as it often attaches to non-verb elements. In fact, *-lik* cannot be applied directly to a gerund in a way *-ghan*, *-sh* and *-maq* can as in (26), which further indicates its idiosyncrasies. Nonetheless, as the examples in (27) suggests, *-lik* is a proper nominalizer because it can be followed by accusative case marker *-ni* and possessive marker *-i* when the verbal gerund is suffixed with another nominalizer (where *-ghan* is often observed). Since this squib is mostly on nominalizations, we will not further explore *-lik*'s versatility but focus on its nominalizing use.

(23). دوكتورلۇق ئۇنۋانى

Doktor-luq unwani

Doctor-LIK degree

‘Doctorate.’

(24). ئۇزۇنلۇق

Uzun-luq

long-LIK

‘Length’

(25). داۋاملىق

Dawam-liq

continuity-LIK

‘Continuously.’

(26). يېيىلىك *

*yey-lik

eat-LIK

‘To eat’

(27). مەن ئۇنىڭ كەلگەنلىكىنى بىلىمەن

Men [u-ning kel-gen-lik-i-ni] bil-i-men

I (s)he-GEN come-PERF-NOML-POSS.3rd.ACC know-PRES.1st

‘I know that he came.’

Readers may have noticed that (27) only minimally differs from (4) by adding *-lik* to the

end of the verb complex and their translation can be identical. In fact, with the incorporation of *-lik*, the factiveness of the proposition is amplified, which carries an additional layer of factuality or abstract state meaning. Based on its accessibility to case markers and possessive suffix, Tuohuti (2012) claims that *-lik* in (27) is a nominalizer; meanwhile, since *-lik* is attached to the uppermost position of a finite clause, Asarina and Hartman (2011) argue for its complimentizer status. We will address this matter in Section 3.4.

2.2.5 The difference of nominalization strategies between Japanese and Uyghur

On the level of eventive and generic oriented nominalizations, Japanese and Uyghur are very much alike regarding the temporal form of the predicate. Specifically, predicate cannot take tensed forms. The Uyghur examples of (11) and (16) make this point very clear. In the same vein, Japanese *koto*, when denoting eventive or generic content, would attach to a non-finite verb:

(28). *私はパンを食べたことが好きだ
 *watashi-wa pan-o tabe-ta-koto-ga suki-da.
 I-TOP bread-ACC eat-PAST-NOML-NOM like-be
 Intended reading: 'I like that I ate some bread.'

(29). *パンを食べたことはいい
 *pan-o tabe-ta-koto-wa ii.
 bread-ACC eat-PAST-NOML-TOPgood
 Intended: 'It is good that some bread gets to be eaten in the past.'

The above awkwardness is expected because event or generic-level nominalizations do not entail TP (Hara et al. 2013 assume that event can be represented by AspP). However, Uyghur *-ghan* shows significant difference from propositional *koto* in that it is by nature a participle which yields clausal nominalization, suggesting *-ghan* encodes tense/aspect by itself; whereas *koto* can follow either simple past verbs or present continuous verbs, as illustrate in (29-30), marking its higher structural position than *-ghan*.

(30). 彼が来たことを知っている
 Kare-ga ki-ta-koto-o si-tteiru
 he-NOM come-PAST-NOML-ACC know-CONT
 'I know that he came.'

(31). 彼が日本語を勉強していることを知っている
 Kare-ga Nihongo-o benkyosi-teiru-koto-o si-tteiru
 he-NOMJapanese-ACC learn-CONT-NOML-ACC know-CONT
 'I know that he is learning Japanese.'

Another fact to notice is that lower *koto* and *-sh/-maq*, though basically on par in terms of semantic interpretations, do have one evident morphosyntactic difference. On one hand,

koto always select an infinite predicate, on the other hand, *-sh/-maq* are part of an infinite predicate. Put this informally, *-sh/-maq* can be seen as something like Japanese *-ru*.

3. Proposals

Given the linguistic data presented above, we propose that Uyghur aligns with Japanese in the sense that both languages employ nominalizers at different structural positions to render various types of nominalizations: eventive, generic or propositional. The key difference is that Japanese has an omnipotent nominalizer *koto* that is capable of enclosing all three kinds of nominalizations while such distinct nominal interpretations in Uyghur depend on separate nominalizers. Additionally, Uyghur nominalizers constitute the predicate (with the force of nominalization being more like a by-product), while Japanese *koto* is adjoined to an infinite predicate which can be used separately with or without *koto*.

We concur the discussion on *koto* by Hara et al. (2013), according to whom *koto*'s ambiguous interpretations stem from its ambiguous syntactic distributions, but their analysis cannot be directly applied to the data of Uyghur given the aforesaid differences. Instead, we propose that Uyghur nominalizers are functional heads merged to distinct positions at distinct derivational stage. For *-ghan*, we propose that it merges to AspP after the first phase is transferred where it initializes the process of nominalization, ensuring that it ranges over the entire proposition. On top of this, *-ghan* would agree with a definite T head to determine its temporal reference; For *-sh*, we propose that it merges to v*P, where it envelops the argument structure (including subject). Following that, we propose *-maq* merges to verbal Root level, where it can hardly access the external argument (see Grimshaw 1990, Alexiadou 2001). For *-lik*, we propose that it appears as a N head merged to a position between AspP and TP before the entire TP be nominalized by a distinct head, either $D_{\text{gen(itive)}}$ or C.

3.1 *-ghan*: the Asp head that is not independently category-defining

First, let us observe how *-ghan* enters syntax and yields nominalization. An intuitive question one may have is: since *-ghan* is a suffix with multiple functions, is *-ghan* surfaced by independent lexical entries? Our answer to this question is **no**. As the sentence in (4), repeated here as (32), indicates, when *-ghan* is directly followed by case makers *-ni* and possessive suffix *-i*, it still unilaterally encodes temporal information. It would be vastly redundant to assume that there are two different *-ghans* in the Lexicon with one being a pure perfectivity indicator while the other being a perfectivity marker plus nominalizer. Therefore, we assume *-ghan* per se merges to a derivation as Asp(ect) head, and the gerund-like use in (4) stems from a higher functional category-defining head *n* (see Marantz 2001, Alexiadou 2001). If defensible, (32) may fall into the structure sketch in (33).

(32). ئۇنىڭ كەلگىنىنى بىلىمەن.

u-ning	kel-gen-i-ni	bil-i-men
(s)he-GEN	come-NOML-POSS.3rd-ACC	know-PRES-1st
'I know that he came.'		

(33). [_{D_{gen}P}[_{TP} he [_{D_{poss}P} [_{D_{poss}} { φ : 2nd} [_{nP} [_{AspP} come ghan]]]]]]]]⁵⁶ (linear order irrelevant)

Upon the completion of (33), the subject may be raised from lower v*P to a higher Spec, D_{gen}P position and from where it receives the genitive case; to implement this idea, one possible analysis is to assume that the subject undergoes phase-piercing successive-cyclic movement all the way to Spec, D_{gen}P through Spec, nP and Spec, D_{poss}P. This approach seems feasible and is attested in the literature (see Asarina 2009 for Uyghur data). Here, we will take the liberty to prove that the recent theoretical refinement called Box Theory by Chomsky (2023) can properly address this issue without appealing to such successive movement.

According to Box Theory (BT), the internal argument *who* in English sentence like “Who do you think that John said that Mary met?” no longer undergoes all the cross-phase movements to be surfaced in the matrix clause. Quite oppositely, it only moves to Spec, VP (V refers to the semantic root of a verb) and remains boxed hereafter. It not only no longer moves, but also stranded from the ongoing derivation and the argument structure. However, the boxed internal argument would still be accessible to higher phase heads (e.g., C) and its discourse-related interpretation and phonological realization are made possible by the interaction between the boxed element and such higher phase head. Therefore, following the BT, we may expect the following derivation:

(34). [_{CP}... [_{AspP} [_{v*P} [_v [_{VP} [_u [_V, u]]]]]]]]

Notice that verb like *kel* “come” is an unaccusative verb, which is generally analyzed as originating in the internal argument position (i.e., VP complement) (Perlmutter 1978; Burzio 1986). After *u* gets boxed, we propose that it can be accessed by three higher phase heads: v* and D_{gen}/D_{poss}. Specifically, v*’s access of *u* gives rise to the phonological linearization of *u kel*; D_{gen}’ access of *u* would grant the genitive case of it, rendering *uning*, D_{poss} would do so to acquire *u*’s φ -specification (i.e., 3rd singular), which ultimately surfaces as *-i*, the possessive suffix to *kel-gen*⁷.

⁵ One may wonder why there must be a DP on top of nP, which should by theory be able to function as a nominal. We believe that DP is needed here because the accusative case marker *-ni* is only applied to definite nominals, suggesting a DP layer is here to license the referential expression.

⁶ Also note that sentences like (32) is often considered to be TP-nominalization and according to Borsley and Kornfilt (2000), such nominalization only occurs above TP. We will leave the question regarding the defectiveness of T open.

⁷ Here we do not make comments on the situation in which an unergative verb is involved. According to Chomsky’s (2023) new definition of phase, external argument (subject) is no longer in the same phase domain that includes v* and VP. Although he does not explicitly present an analysis for intransitive verbs, one may assume that nothing gets boxed in such structures. An immediate consequence would be that a sentence like “Who do you think Mary said took a picture?” would need a different approach from the one argued in the BT. It would be out of the scope of the current work to address such issue, but we can try to make a brief explanation.

The theoretical motivation for boxing an element is to accommodate the essence of Duality of Semantics, which can be paraphrased informally as follows (among many of its interpretations):

- (iii) Each inscription in a derivation only moves (internal merge) once.

If an internal argument becomes boxed in its very landing position after move, one would expect the external argument may also be boxed when it moves to Spec, TP, probably for labelling purpose. If

Before ending this section, we further propose that *-ghan*, merged as Asp head, does not reject simple past tense (Arisana 2009 argues against TP in nominalized verbs). As noted by Li (2025), *-ghan* is not a consistent past tense marker but a perfectivity participle. We then propose that its inherent perfectivity comes from its being an Asp head, but once there is a proper T in the derivation, the T head may contribute to the past tense reading (as Li writes: ‘the past meaning ... through the presence of a null past tense morpheme’). To explicate the mechanism of marking past tense, we propose that when a non-defective T head is in the system, it merges right above AspP. Why would the perfectivity reading be overwritten in such cases? One possible theory is that since Asp and T are technically in the same phase, the interfaces would always detect T before Asp, once the past tense information is fed to the interfaces, it would stop from detecting temporal encoding, including Asp.

3.2 *-sh*: the nominalization enclosing v*P

Recall we have shown that *-sh* is a nominalizer that encompasses a whole argument structure but rejects any temporal references. Thus, it is only naturally to treat it as a v*P-level nominalizer. Asarina (2009) treats both *-sh* and *-lik* as allomorphs, but their difference does stand out as we have clarified in previous sections. As previously stated, we propose *-sh* is a v*P-level nominalizer, lower than *-ghan* and *-lik*. We may have to resort to indirect methods to show that *-sh* is lower than *-ghan* because they cannot cooccur. But it is not the case with *-lik*, which must be structurally higher than *-sh*:

(35). ئۇنىڭ كىتاب ئوقۇشلىقى ياخشى.

uning	kitab	oqu-sh-liq-i	yaxshi
(s)he-GEN	book	read-NOML-NOML-POSS.1 st	good

‘His reading (ability) is good.’

Compared to a *lik*-less sentence, what is presented in (35) incorporates an ability/habit reading and such reading is subject to change based on contextual settings. Therefore, we do not take *-sh* and *-lik* to be allomorphs as they generally do not cooccur (e.g., *-lik* vs. *-liq*).

Yet, it is not completely clear to us whether there is a phonologically null *n*P above *-sh*, or *-sh* is the category-defining *n* head, and our proposal does not hinge upon the specific DP/*n*P layering. Tentatively, based on its sheer category-defining/converting nature, we

plausible, it is reasonable to assume that the subject does not move any further (given it has already reached TP-level, it is unnecessary to assume it is immune to the theta-assignment system), and higher phase heads access it at this very position. This analysis may even potentially account for the that-effect, that the ungrammaticality of (iv) may come from the appearance of C⁰ *that* because if C head is present, Spec, TP cannot be a phase-edge position. In other words, even if it is unproblematic to assume the external argument merged to this position is boxed, it would not be accessible to higher phase head, so *who* can never be spelt-out at sentence-initial position. On the contrary, if C⁰ *that* is absent, its phasehood would then be inherited by T, making Spec, TP a phase-edge position which guarantees the accessibility to Spec, TP.

(iv) *Who₂ does John think that who took a picture.

assume it is *n* head by itself (contra the analysis of *-ghan*). Therefore, the nominalization induced by *-sh* would look like the following structure:

(36). [D_{genP} [D_{possP} i [n_P sh [v*_P u [VP read book]]]]]]

Again, we do not elaborate on the precise mechanism of the case-marking of the genitive subject *u* and possessive gerund *oqush* in (36). As far as we know, the BT-approach discussed above may give a hint.

3.3 *-maq*: Root-level nominalization

Let us now turn to *-maq*, a nominalizer that generally repels overt subject, as (14), repeated here as (37), demonstrates. It would sound awkward if a subject is included, and this leads us to a conclusion that *-maq* is better analyzed as a generic nominalizer that cannot be extended to event-level.

(37). نان يېمەك ياخشى.
 Nan ye-mek yaxshi.
 Bread eat-NOML good
 'Eating bread is good.'

It is worth noting that *-maq* is not completely incompatible with a subject, that as Sugar (2019) observes, *maq*-suffixed verb can accompany a subject when followed by a locative case marker, see (38):

(38). مۇئەللىم دەرس ئۆتۈپتەكەندى.
 Mu'ellim ders öt-mek-te idi
 teacher class teach-NOML-LOC was
 'The teacher was teaching class.' (Lit. The teacher was in the teaching of a class.)

What (38) suggests may constitute an apparent counterargument to our proposal, because *-maq* is responsible for a nominalization that contains a subject. However, such expression is contingent upon the existence of copula *idi* "was". Since the subject *mu'ellim* is in fact an argument of the copula, it is not enclosed by the *maq*-nominalization. Assuming copula in Uyghur is the head of Pred(icate)P, following Sugar (2019), (38) can be formalized under the structure depicted in (39).

(39). [TP teacher [PredP be [D_{PLoc} [v*_P Generic Op [v* [n_P maq [VP teach class]]]]]]]]

One may wonder why we do not assume *teacher* to be the external argument merged to Spec, v*_P. The reason is, as we have argued in 2.2.3, *-maq* is usually associated with generic/event type reading, thus the nominalized content should not include subject *mu'ellim*. With Spec, v*_P being occupied by a Generic Operator, the correct interpretation

attains (i.e, the teacher is in a state, where a teacher is teaching a class). Then what theta-role does *mu'ellim* have and what assigns this role to it? We argue it is the locative predicate (copula + DP_{Loc}) that assigns locational theme role to the subject, very much akin to “John is at home” in English.

3.4 *-lik*: nominalization on clause edge

Recall we have briefly addressed the high productiveness of *-lik* in 2.2.4, and what marks its uniqueness is the wide range of category-defining function spanning from nominal to adjective and adverb, as shown in (23-25). Again, one may draw a quick conclusion that there are multiple distinct *-likes* in the Lexicon that are responsible for its versatility. In this squib, similar to what we have proposed for *-ghan*, we argue there is only one *-lik* and its various category-defining power actually comes from a higher functional head above it. That being said, *-lik* in (27), repeated as (40), is not the head of *nP* but an ordinary N head that merges to AspP (which would be overtly realized in syntax if *-ghan* occurs), just like any other canonical nouns.

- (40). مەن ئۇنىڭ كەلگەنلىكىنى بىلىمەن
 Men [u-ning kel-gen-lik-i-ni] bil-i-men
 I (s)he-GEN come-PERF-NOML-POSS.3rd.ACC know-PRES.1st
 ‘I know that he came.’

Observe that *-lik* in (40) is also followed by the 3rd person possessive marker *-i*, just like a regular genitive-possessive construction. Since it is generally accepted in the literature that the genitive subject in such constructions among Turkic languages occupies Spec, TP (see Kornfilt 2003 for example), *-lik* cannot be located at a position surpassing TP. If our analysis for *-ghan* that it is the Asp head is on the right track, it is desirable to take *-lik* to be an N head somewhere between TP and AspP. Finally, a DP or CP (we leave the exact detail open) above TP completes the nominalization:

- (41). [D_{genP}[TP he [D_{possP}[D_{poss} {q: 2nd} [NP lik [AspP come ghan]]]]]]

Given the above account, the adjective or adverb derivative forms of *-lik* may be resorted another category-defining head like *adj* or *adv*, while the sentence-final use would be generated exactly like (41), in which *-lik* is merely an N head and can readily be suffixed by possessive marker *-i* without any problems.

Conclusions

In the present work, we have compared the nominalization strategies employed by Uyghur *-ghan/sh/maq/lik* and Japanese *koto*. Unlike *koto*, which is capable of enclosing a variety of syntactic entities and converting them into nominals, Uyghur is dependent on different types of nominalizers to accomplish the same target. Specifically, we concur with

Hara et al. (2013) who argue that the semantic ambiguity of *koto* stems from its ambiguous syntactic distribution, and we show that nominalizers in Uyghur that display many differences in terms of semantic interpretations, merge to distinct syntactic positions respectively. In a nutshell, despite all the superficial appearances, Japanese and Uyghur align with each other regarding the cooperation between syntax-semantic components.

As briefly addressed in 3.1, the genitive-possessive construction in Uyghur (perhaps other Turkic languages as well) may receive a universal account from the Box Theory formulated in Chomsky (2023), and it will be our future plans to carry out future examinations of a refined and complete rendition of such analysis.

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